

ADVICE AND SUGGESTION LETTERS; HOW TO WRITE AND ANALYSES.

Feruza Ashurova Maxamadyusupovna

English Teacher at Academic Lyceum under
Fergana State University

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, there is an increasing focus on language learning and there are many types of tests that determine the level of language proficiency. In their work, IELTS and CEFR are undoubtedly the most common, and in these two types of tests, the test taker is asked to write a letter in the writing section. In this article, I am going to give you a complete overview of the most popular type of advice letter.

Key words: A letter, Informal, Semi-formal, Formal, Advice letter, Introduction, Greeting, Body, Conclusion, Closing remarks, Opening Remarks, Dear Sir/Madam, Faithfully, Sincerely, Appropriate language.

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi kunda til o'rganishga e'tibor kuchayib bormoqda va ko'plab til bilish darajasini aniqlovchi test turlari mavjud. Ular ishida shubxasiz IELTS va CEFR eng keng tarqalgan bo'lib bu ikki test turida test topshiruvchidan yozish bo'limida xat yozish so'raladi. Ushbu maqalomda men eng ommabob bo'lgan maslahat turi xati haqida to'liq ma'lumot bermoqchiman.

Kalit so'zlar: Maktub, Norasmiy, Yarim rasmiy, Rasmiy, Maslahat xati, Kirish, Salom, Tana, Xulosa, Yakunlovchi so'z, Kirish so'zlari, Hurmatli janob/Xonim, Sodiq, Hurmat bilan, Tegishli til.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время все больше внимания уделяется изучению языка и существует множество типов тестов, определяющих уровень владения языком. Конечно, IELTS и CEFR являются наиболее распространенными в этих двух типах тестов. В этой статье я собираюсь чтобы предоставить вам полную информацию о наиболее популярном типе рекомендательного письма.

***Ключевые слова:** Письмо, Неформальное, Полуформальное, Официальное, Рекомендательное письмо, Введение, Приветствие, Основная часть, Заключение, Заключительные замечания, Вступительные замечания, Уважаемый господин/госпожа, Верно, Искренне, Соответствующий язык.*

Many language exams, including IELTS General and CEFR exams, require you to produce a letter responding to a given situation within the time limit. Letters can be informal, semi-formal, and formal.

Informal letters are written to people who you know well (friends, relatives).

Semi-formal letters are written to persons you know on a professional (not person-

al) level, e.g. your colleague, your college tutor, etc.

Formal letters are written to persons you only know in a professional capacity and

do not usually interact with, or persons you do not know but need to interact with for some professional purpose. Formal letters also include letters written to government departments, businesses or media, instead of a known individual.

In the CEFR or IELTS General tests of eligibility for monthly salary bonuses and B2-level certification test, you are asked to write a semi-formal or a formal letter. However, IELTS General tests exam and some international language exams may ask you to produce an informal letter as well.

Even though your question may be on any number of topics, you will most likely need to write one of the following six letter types:

1. A letter of request
2. A letter of condolence
3. A letter of appreciation
4. A letter of advice, feedback or suggestion
5. A letter of apology
6. A letter of complaint

1. Greeting. { Dear Sir/Madam,

2. Introduction { I am a third year history student and am writing to you regarding a problem I regularly encounter when I visit the assignment submission desk in the Language Building.

3. Body 1 { Although the Lorne Building is a beautiful and historical campus landmark, it does not provide access to disabled students. As the assignment submission desk is on the ninth floor of the building, my classmate, who is in a wheelchair, is unable to access it. This means that whenever he wishes to hand in an assignment, he must request a classmate do it for him. This, as I am sure you can understand, is both tedious and embarrassing for him.

4. Body 2, request or demand, { My friend is much too proud to contact you directly, so I am writing on his behalf. I am requesting that you promptly alter this building in a manner that allows disabled students to access college resources as conveniently as everyone else. Perhaps this could best be accomplished through the installation of an elevator.

5. Conclusion { I look forward to hearing back from you soon,

6. Closing { Sincerely or Faithfully, Full name.

1. **The greeting** is the greeting portion of the letter. On the IELTS exam, this portion will be written for you. Common salutations you will see on your exam are: To whom it may concern, Dear Sir or Madam,

2. **The Introduction** is the short paragraph that you will write to tell your reader why you are writing. This section is typically only 1 or 2 sentences long.

3. **The body**, the situational details paragraph, is the portion of the letter where you will expand and explain the particulars of your position to your reader.

4. The statement of **request** is the part of the letter where you declare what you hope will be accomplished as a result of your writing.

5. **Conclusion**. The farewell is the few words you write to close your letter.

6. **Closing**, showing your lexical abilities in English to your examiner.

As you can see each of 6 parts of the letter carries specific job. At the end result is a cohesive piece of work that delivers a message in a concise manner. Regarding length, often students think writing extremely long responses of 200 or more words is a strategy that will impress their examiner. Being concise and demonstrating to your examiner that you can express yourself completely in very few words is a better display of your English mastery. Thus, in the lead up to your exam, practice writing in a manner that produces responses of 150 to 170 words. This strategy will also help you conserve time.

Letters of advice, feedback or suggestion or asking for or giving advice can be formal, informal or semi-formal depending on the situation. In a letter asking for advice, you should mention details of the problems. In a letter asking for advice, you should give suggestions introduced with appropriate language.

Useful Language for Formal and Semi-Formal Letters Asking for Advice:

Opening Remarks:

I am writing to ask if you could help me with ...

I would appreciate it if you could give me some advice about...

I am writing to ask for your advice

I would be grateful if you could offer your advice

Closing Remarks:

I would appreciate it if you could give me your advice as soon as possible

I look forward to receiving your advice

It would be of great help if you could advise me

Useful Language for Formal and Semi-Formal Letters Giving Advice:

Opening Remarks:

Thank you for your letter requesting...; I am writing in reply to your letter asking for advice about...; I hope the following advice will be of some help to you

Suggestions:

I strongly recommend that...; I would suggest that...

I believe the best course of action is ...; I would advise you to ...

You should/You ought to/If I were you I would ...

Closing Remarks:

I trust you will accept this advice; I hope this will be of help

I would very much like to know if this was helpful.

Sample Letter Asking For Advice (Sample 1):

Dear Tom Atkinson,

Your advice is needed on a matter of great concern to the employees at the local manufacturing facility. It seems the constant rumors of a corporate takeover are filtering down to the general work force, and the loyalty may soon falter. Some employees have been submitting their applications to our competitors. This could create problems if not dealt with now.

Some sort of official statement to the employees should be made and hope for your guidance as to the content there of.

Your thoughts and advice on this most sensitive matter would be greatly appreciated.

Yours sincerely,

Feruz Lorens.

Sample Letter Giving Advice.

Dear Mr. Watson,

You have asked for my advice regarding the conflict and misunderstanding between you and John Doe. Differences in personality can create very strained relations in an office.

I realize that you have tried to discuss your differences with John, without success. I appreciate your concern and your efforts to resolve the problem. I plan to meet with

John this afternoon to discuss the situation. Then, if I consider it appropriate, I will arrange a time when the three of us can get together, clear the air, and find a way for everyone to be able to work together.

Again, I want to express appreciation for your concern and your desire to establish a more congenial relationship. I will speak to you further about the matter after John and I have met.

Sincerely,

Bob Smith.

Grammar, vocabulary and understanding main idea of the given task are important in writing any letter, so a letter written based on the rules, with a proper understanding of whom is writing the letter to and for what purpose, is always highly appreciated.

LITERATURE

1. *IELTS Writing General task 1: how to write band 9 letters* by Daria Lacy, 2018
2. ielts-mentor.com/writing-sample/gt-writing-task-1/3555-....
3. <https://ieltsmaterial.com/ielts-general-writing-task-1-practice-test-30/>
4. *General training task 1* by Cambridge IELTS consultants 2014
5. cambridgeielts@outlook.com
6. *EXAM SKILLS FOR TEACHERS AND LEARNERS OF ENGLISH* by K.Djalilov. 2016.